

Code, Context, Canon: A Transferable Framework for Computational Canon Studies

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The canon of ancient authors has developed through centuries of scholarly tradition that has shaped textual authority. But how is this canon reproduced in our current means of knowledge transmission, for example in academic discourse? To answer this question, we adapt the scientific paradigm of *knowledge entity extraction* (Zhang et al., 2021): the principle that intellectual information in scholarly texts is conveyed not only through bibliographic strings (Romanello et al., 2009) but also through in-text entities. For the study of the classical canon, valuable “knowledge entities” are author names and work titles from Greek-Roman antiquity – what we call canonical references. However, since canon is also the idea of transcending disciplinary boundaries, we require transferable methods that can scale well from classics to other disciplines with notably less canonical references. What are the possibilities of transferability of computational methods for the study of canonisation? We address this in three steps of our workflow: code, context, and canon.

This poster addresses the DHd 2026 themes of reusing and adapting algorithms to open new research directions. Primarily we are working with an English academic corpus of 16 different disciplines extracted from JSTOR (Luhmann and Burghardt, 2022) inside the context of the PhD network MECANO. In MECANO, we study canonisation processes of authors from Antiquity across multiple dimensions: disciplinary contexts (medical texts, historiography), genres (press articles, encyclopedias), temporal periods (Antiquity, medieval, 18th century), materiality (printed books, digital editions), and data types (both text and metadata). Canon theory so far has demonstrated cross-disciplinary applicability: canon theories in comparative literature (Damrosch, 2006) have also been proven in contemporary literary criticism (Algee-Hewitt and McGurl, 2015) and education (González et al., 2021). Therefore, reusability and transferability should be two key concepts that lead research in canon studies, in order to maximise the impact of research

and contribute back to the broader field of knowledge formation and textual transmission.

Code: Building Transferable Extraction Methods

Entity extraction represents the most code-intensive workflow step. Being canonical references in-text information, the problem can be framed as a Named-Entity Recognition task. Digital Humanities approaches lag behind state-of-the-art computer science models, relying on keyword search (Petrovich et al., 2024), or on high amount of annotated data, for example to train BiLSTM models with a final CRF layer (Lample et al., 2016; Alves et al., 2018). Neither approach transfers effectively to our interdisciplinary corpus. Dictionary-based searches of ancient authors generate substantial disambiguation challenges outside classical studies – manual verification of 200 matches in statistical texts yielded only 50% true positives. Similarly, supervised models exhibit strong dependencies on the texts they were trained on. In contrast, the capabilities of generative Large Language Models (LLMs) have not yet been fully explored.

Beyond this tension between traditional and disruptive approaches lies a further consideration: domain-specific or general models? Domain-specific models (see XLM-RoBERTa for Classics; Najem-Meyer et al., 2025) demonstrate high reusability within classical studies but poor transferability to other contexts. Our goal is using models with general language understanding instead. This dichotomy can be reformulated as zero-shot vs fine-tuned approaches: relying on prompts versus working with annotated text to improve performance.

Preliminary results are shown in Table 1. When it comes to identifying authors and work titles in classical studies texts, a Llama model surpasses the dictionary string-matching approach thanks to its ability to detect work titles. Future work should test larger, non-quantised, generative models.

Table 1: Performance of canonical reference extraction in classical studies texts.

Model	Precision	Recall	F1-Score
Dictionary (Ripoll-Alberola et al., 2025a)			
Ancient Author	0.9470	0.5981	0.7331
Ancient Work	-	-	-
Micro avg	0.9470	0.3931	0.5556
roberta_classics_ner			
Ancient Author	0.8793	0.5152	0.6497
Ancient Work	0.3539	0.3539	0.4228
Micro avg	0.5612	0.5189	0.5392
GLiNER (Zarriana et al., 2023)			
Ancient Author	0.7342	0.7030	0.7183
Ancient Work	0.3049	0.5814	0.4000
Micro avg	0.5875	0.6779	0.6295
llama3.1-8b-instruct-q4_0			
Ancient Author	0.8224	0.6313	0.7143
Ancient Work	0.6814	0.6417	0.6609
Micro avg	0.7623	0.6352	0.6930

Context: Mapping Citation Patterns

To study context, we will perform the visualisation of contextual trends and citation patterns. This section of our three-wheel workflow is the most obviously transferable: there exist already numerous examples of citation networks applied to literary studies (Moretti, 2011; Piper et al., 2017) and intellectual history (Wright, 2016), and other methodologies can be transferred, such as citation intent analysis from scientometrics (Qi et al., 2023) or speech act classification from political sciences (Schmidt et al., 2023).

Canon: Understanding Formation and Evaluation Processes

Canon can be interpreted with the results obtained in the previous steps of the workflow. Our analysis (see Fig. 1) reveals intradisciplinary and interdisciplinary canonisation processes: discipline-specific prominence (Euclid, Ptolemy in mathematics) alongside a cross-disciplinary hypercanon in Damrosch (2006) sense (outstanding presence of Plato, Aristotle, Homer) (Ripoll-Alberola et al., 2025a). Applying identical contextual analysis to Spanish academic corpora demonstrates methodological transferability across linguistic contexts while revealing language-dependent canonical variations (Ripoll-Alberola et al., 2025b).

Ancient author rankings by discipline. Horizontal comparison reveals intradisciplinary canonisation: each discipline privileges distinct canonical authors. Vertical comparison shows interdisciplinary canonisation: authors such as Plato and Aristotle consistently rank highly across disciplines.

Conclusion

This research establishes a reusable computational framework for studying cultural authority through the iterative relationship between code development, contextual analysis, and canonical understanding. Our current work focuses on improving reference extraction methods (as the "code" phase is the basis of the further steps). Future work will emphasise "context" through advanced topic modelling and network analysis to better capture citation patterns. Through this transferability, the MECANO project aims to study canonicity from a diverse lens, and at the end of the project, contribute with a general model of canonisation.

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